

Lukasiewicz 25.02.25

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Creation: 02/25/2025 1:47:29 PM
Sample Name: Proszki

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Image

Live Map 1

ElementOverlay

- C K
- O K
- Si K

C K_ROI (123)

O K_ROI (42)

Si K_ROI (50)

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35 Live Time(s): 1 Amp Time(μs): 50 Resolution:(eV) 138

Sum Spectrum

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 11.46 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Net Int.	Error %
C K	87.3	0.01	93.4	11211.8	6.3
O K	2.3	0.01	1.9	518.6	8.4
Si K	10.3	0.01	4.7	1928.3	5.6